

TRAIN LEARNERS TO LEARN ENGLISH LANGUAGE EFFECTIVELY AND INDEPENDENTLY

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Abstract:

This article describes important teaching and learning principles through the whole process on learning English language as a second one. That it is very useful for the learners to learn to advance their control the language in order to do best return for their effort and progress through effective methods of teaching in everyday language teaching process and progress.

Key Words: Language, Knowledge, Receptivly, Individual Learning Advantages, Process, Motivated, Realistic Suggestion, Vocabulary Skills, Useful Activities.

Literature Review:

The English language is continuously changing, much like life. As much as possible the learners should be interested in and exited about learning the language, and they should come to value this learning. As much time as as possible should be spend using and focusing on the second language the native language is uzbek for our students. It depends on their fluency activities and substantial quantities of interesting to provide activities at increasing the fluency with which learners can use the language knowledge they already have, both receptively and productively. Speaking, writing, sound system, vocabulary, grammar should be learned as deeply and as thoughtfully as possible. It helps learners make the most effective use of previously gained knowledge. The teacher, the teachers skill in teaching the language and students chance of success in learning the language plays the most effective role in this process. The learners may work with the learning material in ways that most suit their individual learning styles. The material of the lesson will help learning. It demands to use suitable teaching techniques and procedures and these need to be put together in the lessons. Some lessons might consist of an unpredictable series of activities of an unpredictable series of activities occurs in all or most of the lessons.

Research Methodology:

There are several vantages: the lessons firth are easier to make, because most lessons begin with a brief introduction about the current topic. A listening activity followed by a reading and speaking task. Then the learners plan a report and present their task to the rest of the class. This is followed by another listening activity and the language focus activities. It is also makes the course easier to monitor, to check of all that should be included is there and that accepted principles are being followed. And disadvantages are the following as we think. It is not simply to take suitable material from other courses adapting it as required, but this creates copyright problems.

Analyses and Results:

Key principles need to be applied at this stage. Amount the most important is the amount of time given to learning from speaking and writing, direct study of language features and fluency development. The lesson format needs to be checked against the environment analysis of the course to make sure that the major environmental factors are being considered. Because English course design is not a liner process, it may be necessary to alter the content or sequencing to suit the lesson format and to reader the list of environmental factors. The lessons may require further adjustment at other stages of the course design. Perhaps the most difficult task at this stage is making sure that learning goals of the course are met- that is, that the required language items are well represented and well presented in the course. There are many questions are appearing in the process. There are many question are questions are appearing in the process of learning language may be unsuitable to the students many suggestions are too for my own purposes. What are the better ways to use and to discover in order to know. It deals with problems such as not enough needed textbooks, poorly motivated students sort out all methods of language teaching and selecting usefull techniques, to introduce innovations into language classroom. The question which look for help them in the teaching of the language skills I just fund answers to them. Realistic suggestions sample questions in communicative way are offered for students. I think that it we must be able to give students a lot of exposure to different kinds of natural kids of spoken massages.They will gain in confidance as they learn to understand from the massage and respond to appropriate ways.

Conclusions and Analyses:

Memorising vocabulary lists is not the most effective way to go about learning vocabulary. Sample exercises will also show that there is more to know about a word than its meaning. For example in my article (5; стр 9-Республика илмий-амалий анжуманда”Modern English Educational vocabulary of language teaching and learning Reseachtrants”) which deals with the destinations between words which are close in meaning but not sufficiently differentiated dictionaries and reseach work. There are many basic questions deals with writing, grammar, questions, lesson planning, testing, preparing to national exams of the ministry of Education. Teaching process directly linked (depends on) the process of beginning, a middle, and an end. The overview of this process is shown below:

Needs Assessment and syllabus:

This process I think may call as a classroom research hard work and there are many different useful activities which we may suggest during the lessons for students when they use English language as a second one. They are following:

- Complete with (questions words)
- Complete the story with the verbs
- What do you think about.....
- Match the beginning with the proverb
- Correct the meaning of the sentences
- Make up sentences from the words and phrases
- Do agriculture vocabulary crossword
- Make a list of words deals with agriculture
- Choose the right word
- What are the benefits of the ideas and advices mentiones an article.

It helps students do their bests during independent work. About independent works of students I wrote in my article (“Инглиз тили дарсларида мустақил ишни ташкил қилиш – Республика миқёсидаги илмий амалий анжуман маърузалари тезислари 7;56 бет – Бухоро 1999 й”)

Finally I want to say that the teaching of foreign languages at all levels in Uzbekistan it is very creatively process, which depends on researching current principles and practice during the educational courses problems.

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